

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Cassia Tora*, Linn. Part I.

BY H. SUBBA JOIS AND B. L. MANJUNATH.

Cassia tora (Chakarmarda in Sanskrit) is a shrub which thrives all over the tropical portions of India. Its leaves, seeds and roots find an important place in Ayurvedic medicine. Dymock ("Pharmacographia Indica," 1889, Vol. I, p. 516) maintains that the leaves are rich in a mucilaginous and foetid smelling material, and a decoction of these is taken internally as a gentle aperient. They are also used in the form of poultice to hasten suppuration. Fried in castor oil they are said to form a good remedy against itch and foul ulcers. The roots made into a paste with lime juice constitute a very good remedy against ring-worm. The seeds are also valuable against skin diseases. They are further used by the indigo dyers of Mysore for obtaining certain colour-effects.

A reference to the literature showed that very little work had been done on the chemical constituents of the seeds. Elborne (*Pharm. J.*, 1888-89, iii, 19, 242) has reported the occurrence of a glucoside which on hydrolysis gives a substance resembling emodin. To this he ascribed the medicinal properties of the seeds. However, he has not attempted to isolate it in any quantity in order to establish definitely its chemical character. The present investigation is a more complete and systematic analysis of the seeds.

Preliminary Examination.

In order to obtain a general idea of the solubilities of the various constituents, a sample of the crushed seeds* (50 g.) was extracted successively with the following solvents, and the extracts were dried at 100°.

Petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°)	extracted	5.2%
Ethyl ether		1.2
Chloroform		1.6
Ethyl acetate		2.2
Alcohol		6.2
<hr/>		
Total	...	16.4%

* For the purpose of this investigation it was found necessary to have the seeds collected under close personal supervision because of the simultaneous occurrence of closely related varieties around Bangalore.

A dark brown oil was obtained from the petroleum ether extract. Ethyl ether took out a small quantity of the colouring matter occurring in the free state. The glucoside was obtained mainly in the last two extracts.

The seeds were tested with Prollius's fluid for alkaloids. The results were negative. When distilled with steam 0.008 per cent. of a pale yellow solid was obtained on extracting the distillate with pure ether. This is probably some of the colouring matter. An aqueous extract of the seeds gave tests for the presence of small amounts of reducing sugars and considerable amounts of hydroly-sable polysaccharides. In this solution starch and tannin were absent. The seeds were also tested for the presence of enzymes. The powdered material (100 g.) was shaken up with sufficient water in a stoppered bottle for 48 hours. A considerable amount of carbon dioxide had been formed and the clear supernatant liquid on filtration was found to contain a large amount of reducing sugars and some soluble organic acids, presumably the products of enzyme action.

The Petroleum Ether Extract.

The Fatty Oil.—The oil from the seeds of *Cassia tora* mixed with other substances is regarded as a very useful application in several kinds of skin diseases (Dymock, *loc. cit.*, and Nadkarni, "The Indian Materia Medica," 1927, p. 185). Since no details were obtainable in the literature regarding the chemistry of this oil, it was thought interesting to submit it to detailed analysis. Owing to the low oil content, the seeds (16 kg.) were extracted by means of light petroleum (b. p. 40—60°) in a modified Soxhlet devised by Dr. M. C. T. Katti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 210). After removing the solvent a dark brown pleasant smelling oil (800 g.) was obtained.

The Physical and Chemical Constants of the Oil.

Specific gravity	...	...	0.8969 at 25°
Refractive index	...	...	1.4669 at 25°
Saponification value	...		154.2
Iodine value (Hanus)	...		90.7
Acetyl value	...		9.6
Acid value	...	...	10.8
Reichert-Meisel value	...	...	0.15
Insoluble fatty acids	...		78.5%
Unsaponifiable matter	...	...	5.4%

The oil was saponified with potassium hydroxide. The resulting soap, after extraction with ether to obtain the unsaponifiable matter, was dissolved in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the insoluble fatty acids were liberated. These were separated into the saturated and unsaturated components by Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

Chemical Constants of the Fatty Acids.

Mean mol. wt. of mixed acids	...	...	285.7
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	...	105.2
Saturated acids (Twitchell's method)	...	...	27.2
Unsaturated acids	..	...	72.9
Mean mol. wt. of saturated acids	...	...	272.0
.. .. unsaturated acids	...	...	297.0
Iodine value (Hanus) of saturated acids	...	...	2.5
.. .. unsaturated ..	...	...	142.0

The Unsaturated Acids.—The mixed unsaturated acids were found to be highly coloured. In an attempt to remove the colouring matter they were converted into their methyl esters which were distilled under reduced pressure (1 mm.). The esters passed over between 176° and 182° as a pale brown oil*. A portion of the acids liberated from this was brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", 6th edition, Vol. I, p. 585). No ether-insoluble additive compound was formed indicating the absence of linolinic acid. Among the products of bromination tetrabromostearic acid (m. p. 113-114°) was isolated. Another portion of the mixed acids dissolved in the requisite amount of weak caustic soda solution was oxidised by dilute permanganate. The crude mixture of the hydroxy acids thus obtained was extracted in a Soxhlet, first with petroleum ether to remove unoxidised acids and decomposition products, and then with ether. From this extract, after removing ether and crystallising the residue twice from alcohol, dihydroxystearic acid was obtained (m. p. 113-114°; mol. wt. 313). The re-

(*) The esters were first obtained in five different fractions whose iodine value (Hanus) gradually increased from 117.6 to 141.5. It is interesting to note that the mean mol. wt. of the acids in the different fractions was between 271 and 278. This apparent lowering is probably due to a change in the nature of colouring matter resulting in interference with the titration.

sidue in the Soxhlet after repeated crystallisations from alcohol gave pure tetrahydroxystearic acid (m. p. 158°; mol. wt. 346. Compare Katti and Puntambaker, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 228). As a result of these experiments the occurrence of oleic and linolic acids in the unsaturated acids has been established.

The Saturated Acids.—The mixed acids were only coloured slightly and in order to effect separation into their constituents they were converted into their methyl esters and the mixed esters (125 g.) were carefully fractionated under diminished pressure (1 mm.).

Fraction.	Range of temperature.	Distillate.	Mean mol. wt. of acids from the saponification value.
I	Up to 147°	2.4 g.	262.9
II	147°–150°	6.9	259.2
III	150°–152°	9.1	257.7
IV	153°–156°	23.9	256.8
V	156°–158°	33.8	259.5
VI	158°–162°	3.0	267.1
VII	*165°‡–168°	12.6	268.7
VIII	168°–171°	12.7	278.0
IX	171°–186°	1.1	283.2
X	186°–188°	4.9	298.4
XI	188°–210°	6.3	327.4
XII	Residue including loss	8.8	368.0 (of the purified acid).

Fractions I–V.—From each of these fractions pure palmitic acid (m. p. 62.5°; mol. wt. 256.1) was isolated as the principal constituent. The identity of the palmitic acid obtained was further established by taking a mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen of the pure acid. The filtrates gave a fraction melting at 59–60° (mol. wt. 264).

Fractions VI–IX.—From these fractions was obtained a substance which melted at 62–63° (mol. wt. 285). Repeated recrystallisations from various solvents did not alter either its m. p. or mean mol. wt. Although the mol. wt. corresponded to that of stearic acid, the m. p. was considerably lower. When a mixed m. p. with pure stearic acid was taken considerable depression was observed.

Acid fraction from the filtrates of above had m. p. 57–58.5°, and mean mol. wt. 272).

* Only a few drops of the distillate passed over between 162° and 165°.

Fraction X.—The acid obtained on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 68° (mol. wt. 335·7) and it was noticed that with successive recrystallisations both the m. p. and the mol. wt. began to increase. But it was not possible to isolate any definite acid.

Fraction XI.—On repeated recrystallisations of the acid from this fraction was obtained a substance melting at 74-75° and whose mean mol. wt. was 350. This also proved to be a fraction that could not be resolved by repeated crystallisations (compare Katti and Manjunath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 843).

Fraction XII.—The residue in the distillation flask was found to be very deeply coloured. It was dissolved in alcohol, saponified and the soap was dissolved in excess of hot water. The fatty acid was precipitated by the addition of excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. This acid (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and refluxed with animal charcoal for a few hours. The crystallised product (m. p. 74-75°; mol. wt. 368) was then repeatedly recrystallised from various solvents including acetone and ethyl acetate. Its m. p. rose up to 76—77·5° while the mol. wt. remained the same. A mixed m. p. with pure lignoceric acid was taken and since no difference was noticed its identity was regarded as established (compare Katti and Manjunath, *loc. cit.*, p. 844).

It is interesting to note that although the mean mol. wt. of the mixed solid acids (272) correspond very nearly to that of an equimolecular mixture of palmitic and stearic acids, no trace of the latter was obtained in the above work. Again since no definite acid was found between palmitic and lignoceric acids, it was thought necessary to mix together all the higher acid fractions. except the twelfth, and to fractionate their methyl esters (30 g.) very carefully under reduced pressure (1 mm.).

Fraction.	Range of temperature.	Mean mol. wt. of acids liberated from the esters and recrystallised from alcohol.	M. p. of acids in the last column.
I	152°—155°	253	62—63°
II	155°—160°	259·6	61—62°
III	160°—165°	259·8	
IV	165°—170°	262·0	56·5—57·5°
V	170°—175°	280·6	59—60°
VI	175°—185°	291·7	59—61°
VII	185°—200°	332·6	62—64°
VIII	200°—210°	344·7	72·5—73·5°
IX	Residue.	368·7	74—75°

Thus it was noticed that the lower fractions (I—III) consisted of palmitic acid. The acids obtained from the Fractions IV—VI with successive crystallisations gave increasing mean mol. wts. and melting points. Fraction VIII gave an acid whose mol. wt. remained constant inspite of several recrystallisations. Finally from the residue was obtained a small quantity of 'crude lignoceric acid.' It is interesting to note that acid fraction of mean mol. wt. 350 from the first fractionation (Fraction XI) could not be isolated again. This was taken as a proof that it was a mixture.

Thus from the solid acids palmitic and lignoceric acids only could be isolated.

The Unsaponifiable Matter.

An oily, reddish semi-solid was left behind after evaporating off the ether used to extract the saponified oil. From this a phytosterol (m. p. 133-134°) was obtained in a colourless and pure state after repeated treatments with animal charcoal and recrystallisations from alcohol. Its acetyl derivative melted at 120°. The red oil from mother-liquors of the phytosterol was treated with digitonine. After removing the precipitate, from the residues it was not possible to isolate any other compound.

Thus during this investigation the following compounds were found to be present in the fatty oil.

- (i) Oleic and linolic acids among unsaturated acids.
- (ii) Palmitic and lignoceric acids among saturated acids.
- (iii) Sitosterol in the unsaponifiable matter.

An examination of the other constituents of the seeds of *Cassia tora* will form the subject of a later communication.